

ОПТИМІЗАЦІЯ РЕАКТИВНОЇ ПОТУЖНОСТІ РОТОРНОГО КОЛА МАШИНИ ПОДВІЙНОГО ЖИВЛЕННЯ**Клюєв О.В.***доцент кафедри електротехніки та електромеханіки
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Дніпровський державний технічний університет**м. Кам'янське, Україна***OPTIMIZATION OF THE REACTIVE POWER ROTOR CIRCLE OF THE DOUBLY FED MACHINE****Kliuiev O.,***Ph.D. technical of science, associate professor
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Отримані енергетичні характеристики машини подвійного живлення як функцій її змінних стану та здійснений їх аналіз. Доведено, що коефіцієнти потужності статорного та роторного кіл можна оптимізувати в статичних режимах регулюванням величини модуля потокозчеплення статора та реактивної складової струму ротора. Властивості аналітичних виразів функцій якості екстремального регулювання машини подвійного живлення проаналізовані з урахуванням ефекту насичення магнітопроводу асинхронної машини. Значення потокозчеплення статора, які доставляють максимум коефіцієнту потужності роторного кола у функції моменту навантаження апроксимовані аналітичною залежністю. Тим самим було доведено, що можна уникнути крокових алгоритмів пошуку екстремуму, використовуючи замість них функціональні перетворювачі. Створена математична модель векторної системи керування машини подвійного живлення з контуром екстремального регулювання потокозчеплення по колу статора за допомогою силового транзисторного регулятора напруги. Запропонований нелінійний алгоритм керування цим регулятором. Працездатність розробленої системи керування з наведеними алгоритмами релейних регуляторів і апроксимуючою залежністю перевірена методом математичного моделювання.

ABSTRACT

The energy characteristics of the doubly fed machine as a function of its state variables were obtained and their analysis was carried out. It is proven that the power coefficients of the stator and rotor circuits can be optimized in static modes by adjusting the magnitude of the stator flux coupling module and the reactive component of the rotor current.

The properties of the analytical expressions of the quality functions of the extreme regulation of the doubly fed machine are analyzed taking into account the saturation effect of the magnetic circuit of the asynchronous machine. The values of the stator flux coupling, which deliver the maximum power factor of the rotor circle as a function of the load moment, are approximated by an analytical dependence. Thus, it was proved that stepwise extremum search algorithms can be avoided by using functional converters instead.

A mathematical model of the vector control system of the doubly fed machine with a circuit of extreme adjustment of the flux coupling stator circle using a power transistor voltage regulator was created. A nonlinear control algorithm for this regulator is proposed. The performance of the developed control system with the given algorithms of relay regulators and approximating dependence was verified by the method of mathematical modeling.

Ключові слова: машина подвійного живлення, енергетичні характеристики, функція мети, екстремальне керування, реактивна потужність, коефіцієнт потужності, релейний регулятор, потокозчеплення статора.

Keywords: doubly fed machine, energy characteristics, objective function, extreme control, reactive power, power factor, relay regulator, stator flux linkage.

Introduction. In powerful asynchronous electric drives, it is advisable to regulate the flows of active and reactive power. It is possible to most effectively untie the channels of regulation of the specified types of power with simultaneous regulation of the rotor speed in systems of vector control of electric drives based on a doubly fed machine (DFM) in both the motor and generator modes of its operation [1-3].

The structure of the vector control system of an asynchronous machine (AM) with constant flux coupling may turn out to be irrational, because the stabilization of the vector flux coupling module control system at the level of the nominal value leads to a decrease in the power factor at moments load of the electric drive less than the nominal. The specified drawback is inherent in adjustable electric drives of loading machines with fan mechanical characteristics. The results of the synthesis of the control system, which ensures the maximum power factor of the AM stator circuit with a short-circuited rotor and a variable load moment, are detailed in the article [4].

The energy characteristics of AM with a semiconductor frequency converter in the rotor circuit have already been studied by the authors of the article. For example, in [5], analytical expressions of reactive power as a function of state variables of an asynchronous valve cascade, which is a separate case of DFM, were obtained and investigated. As a rule, a frequency converter with vector control is included in the rotor circle AM with a phase rotor. In such an electric drive system, which received the name DFM, it is possible to divide the rotor current into active and reactive components.

Through the influence channel on the active component of the rotor current, the speed of rotation of the rotor or active power is regulated, and through the influence channel on the reactive component of the rotor current, the reactive power of the stator circuit AM, which is directly connected to the network, is regulated [6-8]. A review of literature sources confirms the existence of a well-established strategy for controlling the reactive power of the DFM, namely, the regulation of the reactive component of the rotor current allows to change the magnitude and nature of the reactive power of the stator circuit of the DFM. At the same time, the DFM can be used in electric drives of powerful turbo-mechanisms, in which the moment on the shaft is proportional to the square of the rotor speed [9]. Then, at

$$Q_s = \frac{3}{2} \text{Im}[\vec{U}_s \vec{I}_s^*] = \frac{3}{2} (U_{sv} I_{su} - U_{su} I_{sv}) = 0. \quad (1)$$

We will analyze the energy characteristics of the DFM according to its equations in the axes oriented along the stator flux coupling vector. Then after transformations of the equations

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{U}_s &= R_s \vec{I}_s + p \vec{\Psi}_s + j \omega_k \vec{\Psi}_s; & \vec{\Psi}_s &= L_s \vec{I}_s + L_m \vec{I}_r; \\ \vec{U}_r &= R_r \vec{I}_r + p \vec{\Psi}_r + j(\omega_k - \omega) \vec{\Psi}_r; & \vec{\Psi}_r &= L_m \vec{I}_s + L_r \vec{I}_r, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

recorded for a stable mode of operation, we obtain the following ratios:

$$U_{ru} - k_s U_{su} = R'' I_{ru} - \frac{k_s}{T_s} \Psi_s - (\omega_0 - \omega) L_\delta I_{rv}; \quad (3)$$

$$U_{rv} - k_s U_{sv} = R'' I_{rv} - k_s \omega \Psi_s + (\omega_0 - \omega) L_\delta I_{ru},$$

where $R'' = R_r + k_s^2 R_s$; $L_\delta = L_s L_r - L_m^2 / L_s$; ω_0 - speed of ideal idle in electric rad/s.

The balance equations of the stator circuit voltages, taken from (2), in projections on the axis u, v in statics will be written as follows:

reduced speeds, when the load on the shaft AM is less than the nominal one, it is possible to optimize the rotor circle of the DFM in terms of reactive power by adjusting the module of the stator flux coupling vector by changing the value of the stator supply voltage. This approach to the management of DFM is described in [10].

Analytical expressions that allow determining the value of the flux coupling that deliver the extremum to the power indicators AM during rotor control are obtained in [5]. However, in this work, the analytical expressions were derived without taking into account the phenomenon of saturation of the magnet wire, which is manifested in the influence of the magnitude of flux coupling on the value of inductances AM. When forming target control functions and in algorithms for finding their extreme values, the saturation effect of the magnetic circuit AM must be taken into account in order to increase accuracy [11].

It is possible to improve the energy indicators of the DFM by changing the flow coupling as a function of the load moment on the shaft AM. In order to optimize the energy processes in the power plant, it is necessary to build, in general, a multi-channel system with independent control of the reactive current, speed and flux coupling of the asynchronous machine, which can be implemented in a vector field-oriented control system with the addition of an extreme regulation circuit. The goal of regulation can be taken to be the achievement of the extremum of some objective function and observation of the drift of the extremum when changing the parameters and state variables of the electric drive.

Purpose and objectives. The task of this article consists in the formation of quality functions of stable modes of operation of the DFM and the study of the properties of these functions in order to obtain the results necessary for the synthesis of control systems DFM, in which it is possible not only to regulate the reactive power of the stator AM by influencing the reactive component of the rotor current, but also to achieve a minimum of the reactive power of the rotor circuit by changing the module of the flux coupling vector of the stator AM in the scheme DFM.

Material and research results. In DFM, by adjusting the reactive component of the rotor current, it is possible to achieve a unit power factor of the stator circuit, which is achieved by fulfilling the condition:

$$\mathbf{U}_{su} = \mathbf{R}_s \mathbf{I}_{su}; \mathbf{U}_{sv} = \mathbf{R}_s \mathbf{I}_{sv} + \omega_0 \Psi_s. \quad (4)$$

Expressions for stator flux coupling, written in projections on the coordinate axis, taking into account that $\Psi_{sv} = 0$, are presented in the form of the following ratios:

$$\Psi_s = L_s \mathbf{I}_{su} + L_m \mathbf{I}_{ru}; 0 = L_s \mathbf{I}_{sv} + L_m \mathbf{I}_{rv}. \quad (5)$$

In the stationary mode, the resistance moment on the shaft AM is equal to the electromagnetic moment

$$\mathbf{M}_c = -\frac{3}{2} N k_s \Psi_s \mathbf{I}_{rv}. \quad (6)$$

If we substitute expressions (4) in (1), then after reduction of similar terms it will be

$$\mathbf{Q}_s = \frac{3}{2} \Psi_s \omega_0 \mathbf{I}_{su}. \quad (7)$$

It can be seen from formula (7) that in the mode of compensation of the reactive power of the stator, it is necessary to ensure the condition that the reactive component of the stator current is equal to zero $\mathbf{I}_{su} = \mathbf{0}$. Then from (5) and (6) the relations for the currents follow:

$$\mathbf{I}_{ru} = \frac{\Psi_s}{L_m}; \mathbf{I}_{sv} = -k_s \mathbf{I}_{rv}; \mathbf{I}_{rv} = -\frac{2\mathbf{M}_c}{3Nk_s \Psi_s}. \quad (8)$$

Let's form the objective functions, the search for the extremum of which can be carried out by the contour of the extreme regulation, subject to condition (1). To do this, let's express the reactive power of the rotor, determined by the formula

$$\mathbf{Q}_r = \frac{3}{2} \text{Im}(\vec{\mathbf{U}}_r \vec{\mathbf{I}}_r^*) = \frac{3}{2} (\mathbf{U}_{rv} \mathbf{I}_{ru} - \mathbf{U}_{ru} \mathbf{I}_{rv}), \quad (9)$$

through the adjustable variables of the electric drive. When substituting expressions for currents (8) and stator voltages (4) into ratio (3) for rotor voltages, taking into account that $\mathbf{U}_{su} = \mathbf{0}$ at $\mathbf{I}_{su} = \mathbf{0}$, after transformations, we obtain the following dependencies:

$$\mathbf{U}_{ru} = \frac{\mathbf{R} \Psi_s}{L_m} + \frac{2L_\delta \mathbf{M}_c (\omega_0 - \omega)}{3Nk_s \Psi_s} - \frac{k_s}{T_s} \Psi_s; \mathbf{U}_{rv} = \frac{1}{k_r} \Psi_s (\omega_0 - \omega) - \frac{2\mathbf{R}_r \mathbf{M}_c}{3Nk_s \Psi_s}. \quad (10)$$

If we substitute the expressions for currents (8) and voltages (10) into formula (9), then after simplifications we obtain the following ratio for the reactive power of the rotor

$$\mathbf{Q}_r = \frac{3}{2k_r L_m} \Psi_s^2 (\omega_0 - \omega) + \frac{2L_\delta \mathbf{M}_c^2 (\omega_0 - \omega)}{3N^2 k_s^2 \Psi_s^2}. \quad (11)$$

The active powers of the stator and rotor are calculated according to the formulas:

$$\mathbf{P}_s = \frac{3}{2} \text{Re}(\vec{\mathbf{U}}_s \vec{\mathbf{I}}_s^*) = \frac{3}{2} (\mathbf{U}_{su} \mathbf{I}_{su} + \mathbf{U}_{sv} \mathbf{I}_{sv}); \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_r = \frac{3}{2} \text{Re}(\vec{\mathbf{U}}_r \vec{\mathbf{I}}_r^*) = \frac{3}{2} (\mathbf{U}_{ru} \mathbf{I}_{ru} + \mathbf{U}_{rv} \mathbf{I}_{rv}). \quad (13)$$

Taking into account (4) and (8), the expression for the active power of the stator will take the form

$$\mathbf{P}_s = \frac{2\mathbf{R}_s \mathbf{M}_c^2}{3N^2 \Psi_s^2} + \frac{\mathbf{M}_c \omega_0}{N}. \quad (14)$$

The active power of the rotor (13) taking into account ratios (8) and (10) is determined by the expression

$$\mathbf{P}_r = \frac{3\mathbf{R}_r \Psi_s^2}{2L_m^2} + \frac{2\mathbf{R}_r \mathbf{M}_c^2}{3N^2 \Psi_s^2} + \frac{\mathbf{M}_c}{N} (\omega - \omega_0). \quad (15)$$

The power factor of the rotor circle is calculated by the formula

$$\cos \varphi_r = \mathbf{P}_r / \sqrt{\mathbf{P}_r^2 + \mathbf{Q}_r^2}. \quad (16)$$

Having isolated from relations (14) and (15) the terms that determine the losses in the windings of the DFM, and summing them up, we obtain the following expression

$$\Delta \mathbf{P} = \frac{3\mathbf{R}_r \Psi_s^2}{2L_m^2} + \frac{2\mathbf{M}_c^2}{3N^2 \Psi_s^2} (\mathbf{R}_s + \mathbf{R}_r). \quad (17)$$

Each of the expressions (11), (16) or (17) can be considered as a function of the quality of stable modes of operation of the DFM. To research these functions, it is necessary to introduce the dependence of the inductance magnetizing circuit on the magnetic flux into their expressions. As a result of the approximation of the universal magnetization curve, the form of the function and its parameters were determined [11]:

$$L_m = 1,504L_{mH} \left(\frac{\Psi_s}{\Psi_{SH}} \right) \text{ctg} \left(\frac{\Psi_s}{\Psi_{SH}} \right) = a \Psi_s \text{ctg}(b \Psi_s), \quad (18)$$

where $a = 1,504L_{mH}/\Psi_{SH}$; $b = 1/\Psi_{SH}$.

If we substitute the function (18) instead of the magnetization inductance into the expressions for active losses (17) and the reactive power of the rotor circuit (11), then in the end we get:

$$\Delta P = \frac{3R_r \text{tg}^2(b \Psi_s)}{2a^2} + \frac{2M_c^2}{3N^2 \Psi_s^2} (R_s + R_r); \quad (19)$$

$$Q_r = \frac{3\Psi_s \text{tg}(b \Psi_s)}{2K_r a} (\omega_0 - \omega) + \frac{2L_\delta M_c^2 (\omega_0 - \omega)}{3N^2 K_s^2 \Psi_s^2}. \quad (20)$$

Formulas (19) and (20) represent the dependence of active losses in the windings of the DFM and the reactive power of the rotor on the flux coupling of the stator, taking into account the phenomenon of saturation of the magnetic circuit. To determine the extreme values Ψ_s , it is necessary to obtain and solve the equations $d\Delta P/d\Psi_s = 0$, $dQ_r/d\Psi_s = 0$. After equating to zero the results of differentiation of expressions (19), (20), we arrive at the equations:

$$\frac{d\Delta P}{d\Psi_s} = \frac{3R_r b \sin(b \Psi_s)}{a^2 \cos^3(b \Psi_s)} - \frac{4(R_s + R_r) M_c^2}{3N^2 \Psi_s^3} = 0; \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{dQ_r}{d\Psi_s} = \text{tg}(b \Psi_s) + \frac{b \Psi_s}{\cos^2(b \Psi_s)} - \frac{8a K_r L_\delta M_c^2}{9N^2 K_s^2 \Psi_s^3} = 0. \quad (22)$$

The solution of equations (21) and (22) relative to the flux coupling at different moments of static load M_c allowed us to construct the graphs presented in Figures 1 and 2. The extreme values Ψ_s are determined only by the moment of load and do not depend on the speed. Calculations were performed for the DFM made on the basis of an asynchronous machine with a phase rotor type 4AK160S4Y3 with the following technical data: $P_n = 11\text{kW}$, $U_{ln} = 380\text{V}$, $n_s = 1500\text{rpm}$, $U_2 = 305\text{V}$. The variables in the figure are given in relative units: $\mu = M/M_H$, $\psi = \Psi_s/\Psi_{SH}$.

Figure 1 - Graph of the dependence of the extreme values of the stator flux coupling on the moment of static load, at which active losses of DFM reach a minimum

Figure 2 - Graph of the dependence extreme values of the stator flux coupling on the moment of static load, at which the reactive power of the rotor circuit of the DFM reaches a minimum

If we define the derivative of expression (16) by Ψ_s and equate the derivative to zero, then after the transformations we get the following identity, which must be satisfied by the values Ψ_s that deliver the extremum of the power coefficient

$$Q_r \frac{dP_r}{d\Psi_s} = P_r \frac{dQ_r}{d\Psi_s}. \tag{23}$$

The expression for the active power of the rotor (15), if we substitute the function (18) into it, will take the form

$$P_r = \frac{3R_r \operatorname{tg}^2(b\Psi_s)}{2a^2} + \frac{2R_r M_c^2}{3N^2 \Psi_s^2} + \frac{M_c}{N} (\omega - \omega_0). \tag{24}$$

If we take functions (20) and (24) and the results of their differentiation and substitute these expressions into equality (23), then after transformations we obtain the equation

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{3R_r M_c^2 \operatorname{tg}(b\Psi_s)}{aK_r N^2 \Psi_s^2} - \frac{9bR_r \Psi_s \operatorname{tg}^2(b\Psi_s)}{4K_r a^3 \cos^2(b\Psi_s)} - \frac{2bR_r L_\delta M_c^2 \operatorname{tg}(b\Psi_s)}{a^2 N^2 K_s^2 \Psi_s^2 \cos^2(b\Psi_s)} + \\ & + \frac{9R_r \operatorname{tg}^3(b\Psi_s)}{4a^3 K_r} - \frac{2R_r L_\delta M_c^2 \operatorname{tg}^2(b\Psi_s)}{a^2 N^2 K_s^2 \Psi_s^3} + \frac{bR_r M_c^2}{aK_r N^2 \Psi_s \cos^2(b\Psi_s)} + \\ & + \frac{M_c}{N} (\omega - \omega_0) \left(\frac{3\operatorname{tg}(b\Psi_s)}{2aK_r} + \frac{3b\Psi_s}{2aK_r \cos^2(b\Psi_s)} - \frac{4L_\delta M_c^2}{3N^2 K_s^2 \Psi_s^3} \right) = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

As a result of solving this equation at given speeds ω and different moments of static load M_c , a family of graphs of the dependence of the extreme values of the stator flux coupling Ψ_s on the moment of load and speed is determined, at which the power factor of the rotor circle DFM reaches an extremum (Figure 3). The close arrangement of the curves indicates that the extreme values of the stator flux coupling for the power factor of the rotor circle are insignificantly dependent on the speed. If we fix the load moments and solve equation (25) at different speeds, the family of curves in Figure 4 is obtained.

All variables in Figures 3 and 4 are presented in relative units: $\mu = M/M_H$, $\psi_s = \Psi_s/\Psi_{SH}$, $\alpha = \omega/\omega_0$. From the comparison of both figures, it follows that the dependence graphs $\psi_s = f(\mu)$ for speeds $\alpha < 0,9$ and $\alpha > 1,1$ are located between the curves for the specified speeds $\alpha = 0,9$ and $\alpha = 1,1$ in Figure 3. For clarity, two dependencies $\psi_s = f(\mu)$ are presented at $\alpha = 0,3$ and $\alpha = 1,5$. At speeds below the synchronous speed, the extreme values of flux coupling are slightly greater than at speeds above the synchronous speed (Figure 4), which is due to the change in the direction of the flow of the active power of the rotor circle when passing through the synchronous speed.

In order to avoid step-by-step algorithms for finding the extremum, which can lead to self-oscillations and a decrease in the stability margin of the electric drive, it is advisable to approximate the characteristics in Figures 1-3 with analytical expressions and use them in the regulation system of the stator flux coupling module. To approximate all curves, it is most convenient to use the arctangent shape function

$$\psi = d_1 + d_2 \operatorname{arctg}(d_3 \mu). \tag{26}$$

The coefficients d_i are found by the method of least squares and, for example, for the second curve from the top ($\alpha = 0,3$) in Figure 3 are equal to: $d_1 = 0,242$, $d_2 = 0,672$, $d_3 = 3,02$.

In the article [10], the following algorithms are proposed for regulating the speed, active and reactive components of the rotor current

$$U_{puh} = -I_{rv}^* \operatorname{sign}[(A_{11} \Psi_s + A_{12} I_{ru})(\omega^* - \omega) - A_{13} \Psi_s p\omega]; \tag{27}$$

$$U_{pca} = \operatorname{sign}[I_{rv}^* - I_{rv}]; U_{pcp} = \operatorname{sign}[I_{ru}^* - I_{ru}], \tag{28}$$

where $A_{11} = \frac{3N^2 k_s}{2JT_1}$; $A_{12} = \frac{3N^2 k_s^2 R_s}{2J}$; $A_{13} = \frac{3N^2 k_s}{2J}$; $T_1 = \frac{L_\delta}{R}$.

In the same work, the possibility of adjusting the stator flux coupling module by changing the stator voltage amplitude is substantiated according to the following algorithm

$$U_s = U_m \text{ if } ((\Psi_s \cos v)^* - \Psi_s \cos v) > 0; \quad (29)$$

$$U_s = 0 \text{ if } ((\Psi_s \cos v)^* - \Psi_s \cos v) < 0;$$

$$(\Psi_s \cos v)^* = \frac{k_f}{T_f p + 1} \text{sign}[\Psi_s^* - \Psi_s - T_{1p} \Psi_s]. \quad (30)$$

This algorithm is implemented by a single-position relay, with the help of which the stator of the motor is connected to the network if the regulated variable is less than the set value, or is short-circuited if the variable exceeds the set value.

Figure 3 - Dependencies of extreme values Ψ_s for the rotor power factor on the load moment at different speeds

Figure 4 - Dependencies of extreme values Ψ_s for the rotor power factor on speed at different moments of load

In the sliding mode, the average value of the error at the input of the relay (30) is zero, and the low-pass filter, made in the form of an aperiodic link of the first order, passes to the input of the regulator (29) the averaged value of the variable $\Psi_s \cos v$, at which the flux linkage Ψ_s will be equal to the required value Ψ_s^* . The reference signal of the flow coupling regulator Ψ_s^* is not formed by an extreme regulator with a step algorithm for finding the extremum, but by a functional converter that implements dependence (26). At the same time, the stator excitation regulation system ensures the maximum power factor of the rotor circle as a function of the moment of static load on the shaft AM. Figure 5 shows graphs of transitional processes in DFM with a three-channel system of control. The mutual connection of the contours control of the stator and rotor reactive powers DFM is determined by the fact that the value of the reference circuit for the regulation reactive current of the rotor is improved by the formula $I_{ru}^* = \Psi_s^* / L_m$ a change in the stator flux according to the specified ratio, the reactive current of the rotor changes.

With the reactive component of the rotor current, which is equal to $I_{ru} = \Psi_s / L_m$, the characteristic of the DFM $I_s = f(I_{ru})$, similar to the V-shaped characteristic, reaches a minimum and the stator current becomes fully active ($\cos \varphi_s = 1$). Thus, the system for regulating the excitation of the DFM from the rotor side is implemented as an extreme control system according to the criterion of the minimum of the stator current module for the current value of its flux coupling.

At reduced rotation frequencies, when the moment of resistance on the shaft AM, created by a mechanism with a fan mechanical characteristic, is significantly less than the nominal one, the amplitude of the stator voltage decreases, which leads to a decrease in the magnetizing current, stator flux coupling and an increase in the power factor of the rotor circle. The power factor of the rotor circuit is calculated as the phase shift angle between the rotor current vector and the additional voltage that is supplied to the rotor phases. On the graphs of the rotor power factor, the number 1 indicates the maximum possible rotor power factor when adjusting the stator flux coupling module by the controller with the algorithm (29), (30) and ensuring the value of the stator flux coupling in stable modes at the level

Figure 5 – Graphs of transient processes in the DFM with extreme control according to the criterion of the maximum power factor of the rotor circle

determined by expression (26) obtained from the solution equation (25) at different moments of load on the shaft AM. Number 2 indicates the graph of the power factor of the rotor in the case of no adjustment of the stator flux coupling at a constant nominal voltage of the stator DFM. The average value of the reactive current of the stator I_{su} is zero, therefore the reactive power of the stator circuit in stable modes Q_s is also practically zero, and in transient processes, when the reactive power of the rotor increases Q_r , the stator circuit generates reactive power to the network. Excitation of the DFM with this control system is carried out exclusively from the side of the rotor. In braking mode, the rotor circuit switches from recuperation of active power to its consumption and is then fed into the network through the stator circuit of the DFM along with the active power generated by the conversion of the kinetic energy of the rotor AM into electrical energy. Despite the change in the moment of load on the shaft of the DFM, the stator flux coupling control system ensures the maximum possible value of the power factor of the rotor circle.

Conclusions. In this paper, expressions for energy indicators as goal functions for extreme control of the DFM were obtained, taking into account the phenomenon of saturation of the magnet wire AM. As a result of the solution of equations (21), (22), (25) by numerical methods, flux linkages of the stator DFM were found, in which the energy characteristics (16), (19), (20) reach an extremum. The dependences of the extreme values of flux coupling Ψ_s on the load moment obtained in this way are best approximated by arctangent dependences with three parameters. In control systems, the algorithms for finding the extremum of the objective functions can be replaced by functional converters that implement expressions of the form (26). The proposed non-linear algorithm for controlling the voltage regulator in the stator circuit DFM, which is included in the circuit of extreme control of the power factor of the rotor circuit. The performance of the developed control system with the given algorithms of relay regulators and functional converters was verified by the method of mathematical modeling.

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